

PERSPECTIVE TRENDS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOOD INDUSTRY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация. В условиях глобализации вопросы продовольственного обеспечения и продовольственной безопасности занимают важное место в экономике страны. Роль пищевой промышленности в развитии производительных сил определяется, прежде всего, тем, что она удовлетворяет преобладающую часть потребностей населения в продовольствии. Пищевая промышленность обеспечивает более рациональное питание населения, способствует устранению неравномерности потребления пищевых продуктов как во времени, так и в региональном разрезе, позволяет эффективно использовать сельскохозяйственное сырье, сокращать его потери.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, пищевая отрасль, аграрный сектор, менеджмент, продовольственная безопасность, бизнес процессы.

Abstract. In the context of globalization, issues of food supply and food security take an important place in the country's economy. The role of the food industry in the development of productive forces is determined, first of all, by the fact that it satisfies the predominant part of the population's food needs. The food industry provides a more rational diet for the population, helps eliminate uneven food consumption both over time and regionally, allows for the efficient use of agricultural raw materials and reduces their losses.

Keywords: globalization, food industry, agricultural sector, management, food security, business processes.

The food industry makes a significant contribution to the development of the economy of Uzbekistan and is one of the main sectors of the economy, protects and supports the population in the social aspect, constantly creates new jobs, and, often, forms the budgets of small and large regions.

Food enterprises in the industry are mainly engaged in the processing of local raw materials, which require constant improvement of the production base, introduction of innovations, and development of supply chains.

Depending on the degree of influence of raw materials and consumer factors, the food industry is divided into three groups:

- industries focused on sources of raw materials (with high rates of raw material consumption) - sugar, oil-processing, canned milk, fat and oil, starch and syrup, etc.;

- industries that incline towards places where finished products are consumed (if the weight of the finished product matches or exceeds the weight of the original raw materials) - bakery, brewing, confectionery, pasta, dairy, etc.;

- industries that are simultaneously focused on raw materials and on the consumer (with a greater weight of raw materials compared to finished products) - meat, flour-grinding, tobacco, etc. (fig. 1).

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i The dynamics of development of food industry sectors is formed under the influence of various factors, which include the determining demand for certain types of food from various social groups and the growth of incomes of the population, as well as the entry of Uzbekistan into the global economic space and the increasing possibility of risks threatening the sustainable and dynamic development of the food industry from the world food market.

Food production in Uzbekistan has been growing dynamically over the past 6 years, increasing by 31% during this period. Investments in fixed capital of the industry also grew dynamically. If in 2017 investments amounted to \$230.7 million, then in 2022 this figure reached \$550.1 million. However, the growth rate of investments was heterogeneous during the observation period, with the largest increase in 2018 (144.3%) and the smallest in 2022 (96.8%).

Important indicators of production of various food products also show positive dynamics. During the period from 2017 to 2022, the production of wheat flour increased by 32%, sugar by 26%, milk and dairy products by 19%, sausages by 21%, pasta by 16%, and margarine by 34%. Over 6 years, employment in the industry increased by 22%, the number of enterprises grew by 224%, and exports increased by 336%.

In general, an analysis of the dynamics of food production in Uzbekistan over 6 years shows positive trends in the growth of production, investment, employment, exports and expansion of production capacity. This can be achieved through improving technology, product quality and promoting the Uzbek food brands on the world market.

These and other innovations are being implemented in accordance with the programs outlined in the Agricultural Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030, adopted by Presidential Decree of October 23, 2019. The main goal of the strategy is to radically improve state policy aimed at deepening reforms in the field of increasing competitiveness of agrifood sector, covering the following strategic priorities:

- ensuring food security of the population;
- creation of favorable agribusiness climate and value chains;

- reducing the role of the state in managing the sphere and increasing investment attractiveness;

- ensuring the rational use of natural resources, environmental protection and other measures.

Thanks to innovations, the number of cotton, grain, and fruit and vegetable clusters increases every year. The integration of science and production is being strengthened. Digital technologies are being introduced into the industry. Regional and international cooperation is expanding, including in the field of specialist training.

Taking into account plans for the further development of the country's agriculture, holding regional and international exhibitions UzAgroExpo, UzProdExpo and InterPackExpo is becoming an important event for the development of the industry, expanding cooperation and international relations.

To increase food production in Uzbekistan in 2023, 6.2 trillion soums have been allocated by a new mechanism. In particular, 700 billion soums have been allocated from the Agricultural Fund to replenish the working capital of fruit and vegetable growing entities. 500 billion soums will be allocated for the supply of seedlings, seeds, fertilizers and agricultural equipment to the lands allocated to the population.

The benefit of these investments lies in the fact that each opened enterprise means additional jobs, the creation of infrastructure, and the attraction of foreign specialists are allocated after introducing the facilities into practice and the execution of relevant acts.

Particular attention is paid to meeting the needs of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for high-quality and safe food products, and the effective development of the food industry. Increasing the volume of processing of fruits and vegetables, meat, milk and other agricultural food products based on international quality standards, introducing a system of state support for the production of local food products that are competitive in the domestic and foreign markets, as well as providing the population with high quality and setting the task of further improving the provision of safe food products.

In this regard, it is desirable to deepen scientific research in such areas as improving methodological approaches to modeling trends in the development of the food industry using contemporary modeling methods. and the ones that model the process of statistical analysis and network modernization, justifying multifactor empirical models for predicting production trends.

Currently, food enterprises are pursuing a policy in the field of IMS (integrated management system) and the main business goal is:

- implementation of the company's vision and mission by methods and the ones that ensure maximum satisfaction of consumers' demands and expectations of and of other key stakeholders;

- production and sale of high-quality and safe food products; reducing adverse impacts on the environment;

- ensuring the efficient use of energy resources, creating safe working conditions for company employees and other persons under its management;

- ensuring a stable economic position of the company and, on the basis of this, increasing the well-being of employees.

The main strategy of enterprises in the field of quality management system is based on:

- the company's activities based on generally accepted principles of quality management and risk-oriented thinking to achieve sustainable development of the company;

- release of own-produced products of stable quality in compliance with all established product requirements;
- effective planning and achievement of indicators established in business plans; ensuring mutually beneficial relationships with consumers, optimizing relationships with suppliers and partners;
- application of effective advertising policy to study consumer demand and promote products, conduct marketing research, organize effective feedback from consumers;
- effective personnel management, creating conditions for motivation and interest of personnel in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of their work; stimulating advanced training of its personnel;
- systematization and accumulation of in-house knowledge, its use to maintain a high professional level of company personnel;
- improving the system of information, normative, methodological and technical support for the company’s activities;
- improvement of trade and technological infrastructure, rational use of the capabilities of existing equipment;
- creating conditions for a higher level of quality control of products of own production.

Improving the strategic behavior of food industry enterprises in the context of globalization is one of the factors in ensuring the country's food security and neutralizing threats to the global economy. In turn, the transformation of strategic behavior is unthinkable without assessing it and determining what strategic actions are taken by enterprises to best adapt to the external environment and how well these actions correspond to the conditions of globalization.

Food security is one of the main goals of the state’s agricultural and economic policies and consists of the following elements:

- 1) physical availability of sufficient, safe and nutritious food;
- 2) economic accessibility to food of the proper volume and quality for all social groups of the population;
- 3) autonomy and economic independence of the national food system (food independence);
- 4) reliability, that is, the ability of the national food system to minimize the impact of seasonal, weather and other fluctuations on the food supply to the population of all regions of the country;
- 5) sustainability, meaning that the national food system develops in a mode of expanded reproduction.

In modern conditions of global instability, competitiveness management of food industry enterprises is becoming increasingly relevant.

As a result, more and more new products are appearing in the country, using the latest methods of organizing the supply of goods. In addition, consumer preferences driven by rising incomes, changing population patterns, and new lifestyles are increasingly influencing the industry.

It has been revealed that, on one hand, the food industry is relatively traditional, and on the other, it is introducing advanced technologies. All these factors influence the development and competitiveness of modern food industry enterprises.

Thus, the food industry is called upon to satisfy the basic needs of the population for essential food products. It is closely connected with agriculture, which is the main source of raw materials for the industry. It is necessary to introduce new technologies in the food and processing

industries, including bio- and nanotechnologies, which will significantly expand the production of new generation products with specified quality characteristics, increase the depth of processing, and involve secondary resources in economic circulation, which will increase the output of finished products per unit of processed raw materials.

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